

Abstract

Several studies and tools have shown that cryptocurrency anonymity can be reduced, enhancing the traceability of the on-chain funds. In response, criminals employ obfuscation techniques to maintain their privacy, with *Mixers* posing significant challenges as they leverage advanced cryptographic primitives to increase anonymity and secure transaction details. These techniques obscure the fund-blending mechanisms within mixers, making it difficult for investigators to trace the flow of the funds. Recognising these challenges, this paper introduces a systematic graph-based approach to analyse mixer activities, characterising their different procedures and *Modus Operandi (MO)*. The methodology uses a modified version of 2-step address-transaction graphs and focuses on three phases: 1) economic analysis of how the mixer receives/sends money; 2) intra-graph analysis of relationships between mixer addresses; and 3) inter-graph community analysis, extracting communities from all the mixers' activity graphs and clustering them according to topological similarities. This approach is validated by analysing the *Blender.io* mixer within the Bitcoin blockchain, revealing three main aspects relevant to defining its *MO*. Firstly, funds are aggregated into a single address, with relevant siblings that receive larger amounts. Then, common patterns suggesting a peeling chain structure are detected, with multiple mixer addresses linked together. Finally, the clustered communities reveal well-established structures in which *Exchanges* are key entities involved in mixer activities. By enabling investigators to manage limited graphs and leveraging a visualisation approach, this methodology aims to provide actionable insights for defining criminal *MO* and targeting enforcement efforts at specific aspects of criminal activities.

Analysing Economic and Topological Patterns in Mixer Activities: Insights from a Case Study

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1 Introduction

The inherent features of cryptocurrency, such as anonymity (or pseudoanonymity in some cases), decentralisation, borderless nature, and the current difficulty in defining clear regulations to control their usage, have made them the preferred medium for facilitating, storing, and paying illicit activities. In fact, according to the *2024 Chainalysis Report* [1], nearly \$40B and \$25B were moved by cryptocurrency addresses involved in illicit activities in 2022 and 2023, respectively.

Several studies [2, 3] have shown that cryptocurrency anonymity can be decreased, enabling Law Enforcement Agencies (LEAs) to use the ‘follow-the-money’ approach for tracking the on-chain activities. For this reason, in some cases, entities use obfuscation techniques to enhance their privacy and anonymity, whose complexity is strongly influenced by the cryptocurrency used, the skills of the user, and the origin (licit or illicit) of the funds [4]. In general, obfuscation methods such as money mules, international bank accounts, or cash transfers, are mainly used in cryptocurrency investment fraud and scams. In contrast, other crimes are more likely to involve complex money laundering networks that exploit Crime-as-a-Service (CaaS) strategies or use specialised services such as mixers, swappers, and decentralised or no-KYC (Know Your Customer) exchanges [1, 4].

Among dedicated services, mixers remain one of the most challenging entities to tackle. This is because their owners are often unwilling to cooperate with LEAs, and technically, they operate as ‘black boxes’. In fact, they leverage advanced cryptographic primitives such as hash functions (for data integrity and unlinkability), zero-knowledge proofs (to ensure anonymity), and commitment schemes (to secure and obscure transaction details) [5]. Together, these techniques enhance user privacy and security, making it exceptionally difficult for investigators to trace the flow of illicit funds [6]. To tackle these challenges, financial authorities such as the US Office of Foreign Assets Control (OFAC)¹, Office of Financial Sanctions Implementation (OFSI)², European External Action Service (EEAS)³, United Nations Security Council (UNSC)⁴, have started

¹<https://ofac.treasury.gov/>

²<https://sanctionssearchapp.ofsi.hmtreasury.gov.uk/>

³<https://www.eeas.europa.eu/>

⁴<https://www.un.org/securitycouncil/content/un-sc-consolidated-list>

imposing sanctions on mixers involved in illicit activities to discourage others from engaging relations with them. *Sinbad*, *Tornado Cash*, and *Blender.io* [7–9] are just a few examples of mixers sanctioned between 2022 and 2023. While this sanctioning strategy decreased funds sent to mixers from illicit addresses, it did not stop user demand. In fact, after that, organised groups like the Lazarus Group have created their own mixer, while former users of sanctioned or shutdown mixers have migrated to new entities such as *YoMix* [1].

Recognising the challenge in understanding how funds are blended [5, 10, 11], and the difficulty in halting mixers’ activities, this work introduces a systematic graph-based approach to evaluate mixer on-chain activities, enabling the detection of its *Modus Operandi (MO)*. This approach proposes three phases to analyse economic and topological patterns using limited graphs (a modified version of 2-step address-transaction graphs) reducing the complexity of the data to be processed. Specifically, Phase 1 checks for economic similarities in the transactions where mixers receive and send funds, while Phase 2 conducts intra-graph relational analysis examining how multiple mixer addresses are connected within the same graph. Then, Phase 3 analyses inter-graph community similarity by extracting dense topological structures using community detection algorithms on all mixer activity graphs, and grouping similar communities using clustering algorithms. Additionally, information about known entities (*Exchange*, *Marketplace*, *Gambling*, etc.) within the communities is used to enrich the findings of this phase. Finally, to validate the results, a graph visualisation tool (Gephi [12]) is used. The methodology has been used to dissect *Blender.io* activities. This mixer operated mainly in the Bitcoin network, and it was one of the first sanctioned mixers in May 2022 by the OFAC, primarily for engaging in malicious cyber-enabled activities (money laundering), as well as for its involvement in activities related to the Ukraine-Russia conflict [7].

In summary, the main contributions of this work are: 1) presenting a systematic graph-based approach to combine economic, inter-, and intra-graph information and create a more comprehensive picture of mixer activities; 2) validating the approach through a specific use case, demonstrating its effectiveness with limited graphs; 3) employing a visualisation approach to evaluate the uncovered patterns and enhancing officers’ ability to interpret the findings and detect mixer *MO*.

The rest of the paper is structured as follows: Section 2 describes related work on mixer analysis and introduces graph analysis concepts. Section 3 outlines the proposed approach, while Section 4 details experiment parameters. Section 5 presents the results, followed by a discussion of the findings and limitations. Finally, Section 6 concludes and suggests directions for future work.

2 Background

This section introduces concepts related to cryptocurrency graph extraction, graph analysis and clustering, along with a review of mixer-related work. Specifically, address-transaction graphs and community detection algorithms are dis-

Figure 1: Example of 1-step address-transaction graph originated from a_y .

cussed in Section 2.1, while clustering strategies are detailed in Section 2.2. Finally, Section 2.3 reviews studies related to mixers.

2.1 Address-Transactions Graph and Community Detection

Blockchain analyses often exploit the intrinsic structure generated by transactions to build an address-transaction graph [2, 13, 14]. This graph is a directed graph $G = (V, E)$, where the set of nodes V consists of blockchain addresses ($a_y \in A$) and transactions ($tx_z \in T$). Then, the directed edges E represent interactions between these entities. Specifically, a directed edge $e(a_y, tx_{z+1})$ indicates that a_y sends funds through the transaction tx_{z+1} (sender relation), while an edge $e(tx_z, a_y)$ reveals that a_y receives funds through the transaction tx_z (receiver relation), as shown in Figure 1.

Both nodes and edges can be enriched with additional attributes such as labels, amounts, fees, timestamps, etc. Additionally, to build this graph, the number of exploring steps n must be defined. This parameter specifies the number of transactions (both backward and forward) to explore from a selected starting point. The resulting graph will include all paths originating from or leading to the starting point, with a maximum length of $2n$. Figure 1 shows the 1-step address-transaction graph when a_x is selected as starting point.

These address-transaction graphs can result in complex and huge networks, where relationships among discrete entities (dynamics) and patterns are harder to extract and analyse. For this reason, it is essential to apply some techniques which are able to decrease graph complexity, allowing for a more efficient analysis.

Among these techniques, Graph Partitioning [15] and Community Detection Algorithms [16] can be highlighted. The first one aims to decompose a graph into smaller, more manageable subgraphs that satisfy certain defined criteria (minimising edge cuts, balancing the sizes of the partitions, etc.) [17]. This approach is usually used for facilitating the parallel execution of analytical and computational processes [15, 18]. The second category aims at identify-

ing strongly interconnected groups of nodes (communities) within the graph, thereby uncovering natural divisions that can be leveraged to distribute computational tasks more efficiently across these communities [16, 19]. Exactly for this reason, community detection algorithms represent a suitable solution for the aim of this study. In fact, by enabling the extraction of communities where nodes are more densely connected internally than with the rest of the graph, these techniques become essential for uncovering structural patterns.

Various community detection approaches have been implemented and compared in the literature, such as Minimum Cut Method, Hierarchical Clustering, Girvan Newman Algorithm, Modularity Maximization in [20], Fast-greedy, Louvain Community (LC), and Walktrap in [21, 22], Clique Percolation, Exploratory Factor Analysis and the Walktrap [23]. Among these, the LC algorithm [24] has become one of the most popular community detection algorithms due to its speed, efficiency, and ability to handle large networks [25, 26]. This algorithm is a non-overlapping community detection method, meaning each node is assigned to only one community. The Louvain algorithm is based on maximising modularity, a measure of how dense the connections are within communities compared to those between communities [24]. Some studies [22, 27] have shown that the LC algorithm, and some of its variants [19, 28], consistently performs well across different networks with different complexity.

2.2 Clustering Algorithms

In the graph-based approach proposed in this study, we are interested not only in uncovering structural topologies (community detection), but also group them according to their similarities and repetitions. For this reason, clustering techniques represent the suitable solutions for this task. Indeed, clustering algorithms are techniques whose main purpose is to group points into clusters based on similarity or distance in a feature space. They are not specifically focused on graphs (they can analyse data points, features, etc.), and can be categorised according to their purpose, methodology, and the type of data they target [29]. Among the different categories, density-based clustering algorithms (DBCLAs) are particularly interesting, as they group data points into clusters based on regions of high data density, rather than predefined shapes or explicit cluster counts [30]. This provides flexibility, robustness against noise, and the ability to detect non-convex clusters in complex analyses [30].

In this study, two DBCLAs are used, and their results are compared: the Ordering Points To Identify the Cluster Structure (OPTICS [31]) and the Hierarchical Density-Based Spatial Clustering of Applications with Noise (HDBSCAN [32]). The first one creates an ordering of points that reflects the underlying clustering structure. It generates a reachability plot that shows the density and connectivity of data points. To do that, it requires the definition of a minimum number of points to create a cluster (*minPts*) and the maximum distance from one point to another for both to be considered neighbours (ϵ). The second algorithm extends the functionality of DBSCAN [33], facilitating the identification of clusters at different scales, which is beneficial for explor-

ing the subgraphs at various levels of granularity. It still requires the *minPts* parameter but it is able to automatically tune the ϵ parameter.

2.3 Mixer-related Studies

Early research primarily focused on developing innovative mixing strategies. Significant examples in the literature include [5, 11, 34], some of which were implemented as public services. On the other hand, a foundational study on understanding the behaviour of existing mixer services was conducted by Moser et al. [35], where the authors performed the first empirical study to evaluate the extent to which Bitcoin mixers enhance user anonymity. Subsequent research has provided more detailed analyses, often emphasising the development of new techniques to identify potential mixing transactions or mixer addresses, but without exploring the underlying *MO*. For instance, heuristics for detecting mixers have been proposed in several studies [36, 37]. Additionally, machine learning and deep learning techniques have been applied to detect mixing transactions. For example, Sun et al. [38] used only economic information to train a Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) network, while Xu et al. [39] implemented ensemble models capable of classifying both transaction behaviours and subgraphs. In [40, 41], strategies based only on topological information were presented. Both studies used outlier community approaches to detect mixing points. Specifically, Prado et al. [40] relied on the fact that mixer users are a minority of blockchain users, therefore, they should present more inter-community connections compared to other users within the same community. However, this approach requires mapping all the transactions into a single graph before performing the analysis, making it difficult to apply to real-world data. The same problem was reflected in [41], where authors use the Local Outlier Factor to analyse graph embedding extracted from communities to detect mixers. Yet, they report that the process was too slow. We et al. [42] extracted information about the frequency of six basic pre-defined subgraphs, economic information, and transaction cycles (ordered pairs of continuous input and output flows) to detect new mixer addresses. However, the authors used yearly transaction graphs that were difficult to manage, did not consider the topological properties within these graphs, and did not highlight which main patterns were used by mixers. A first analysis, aimed at shedding light on mixer’s *MO*, is presented in [37]. The authors categorise mixers based on how funds are redistributed, defining them as swapping when lengthy peeling chains are used, or obfuscating when anonymity sets are employed.

Inspired by these works, this paper proposes addressing some of the previously mentioned limitations by presenting a comprehensive, multi-phase approach to uncover mixers’ *MO*. Specifically, the approach aims to 1) combine economic, inter- and intra-graph information; 2) allow officers to analyse reduced graphs; and 3) leverage a visualisation tool to interpret and validate the uncovered results of a specific case study.

3 Systematic Graph-Based Approach

The goal of this paper is to introduce a systematic graph-based approach to analysing the commonalities and patterns generated by a specific cryptocurrency mixer. To achieve this, the proposed approach evaluates both the economic information and the relationships formed by the mixer within the blockchain. To do that, it is essential to have available a list of labelled mixer addresses that are used as a starting point to build address-transaction graphs. Specifically, this study uses a 2-step graph, where two consecutive transactions (both backward and forward) from the starting point are explored. At the same time, a weight is assigned to each edge, reflecting the amount of money (in cryptos) sent or received (depending on the arrow's direction). Additionally, a modification to the graph creation process defined in Section 2.1 is proposed; if during the 2-step exploration of the mixer address a_y , another labelled mixer address a_{y+1} is discovered, a_{y+1} is used in turn as a new starting point, and its 2-step neighbourhood information is included in the same graph (Figure 2). In this way, we reduce the number of distinct graphs created, since multiple mixer addresses can be interconnected in the same graph, while simultaneously retaining all the necessary information for evaluating their relationships. From the resulting graphs, for each mixer address, it is possible to identify tx_{sout} and tx_{sin} as the transactions where they appear as output and as input, respectively. Finally, labels are also added to the nodes identified in external sources as belonging to other labelled entities such as *Exchanges*, *Services*, *Marketplace*, etc.

Figure 2: Example of modified 2-step address-transaction graph.

Once these graphs are created, they can be dissected and analysed following a systematic approach based on three main phases: i) economic transaction analysis, ii) intra-graph relational analysis, and iii) inter-graph community analysis.

Phase 1: Economic transaction analysis. In this phase, economic attributes are directly extracted from tx_{sout} and tx_{sin} for each mixer address, i.e., the transactions through which the mixer receives and sends funds, respectively. The analysed attributes are: the overall amount sent in tx_{sout} , the portion of it actually received by the mixer address, and the fees. Then, regarding how the funds stored in the mixer addresses are spent via tx_{sin} , the outputs (overall and highest values) of these transactions are dissected and evaluated.

Phase 2: Intra-graph relational analysis. This phase focuses on analysing

Properties	Level	Range	Description
<i># address</i>	Graph	$[1, \infty)$	The number of nodes representing distinct entities (e.g., addresses in a cryptocurrency network)
<i># txs</i>	Graph	$[1, \infty)$	The number of edges representing transactions or interactions among addresses, reflecting the community’s transactional complexity.
<i>transitivity</i>	Graph	$[0, 1]$	The likelihood that the neighbours of a node are interconnected [43].
<i>diameter</i>	Graph	$[1, \infty)$	The greatest shortest path distance between any two nodes in the community [44].
<i>degree</i>	Node (max., min., mean)	$[-1, 1]$	A measure of a node’s importance based on the number of direct connections it has [45].
<i>closeness</i>	Node (mean)	$[0, 1]$	A centrality measure that assesses how close a node is to all others by considering the sum of shortest paths [46].
<i>betweenness</i>	Node (mean)	$[0, 1]$	A centrality metric counting how often a node lies on shortest paths between other nodes [47] .
<i>harmonic (centrality)</i>	Node (mean)	$[0, 1]$	A centrality measure computed as the sum of the reciprocal of distances to all other nodes [48].

Table 1: Graph properties extracted from each community for studying its topology.

the information and relationships within each modified address-transaction graph separately. Firstly, the number of nodes and transactions in each graph is used to conduct an initial analysis of the mixer activities, providing insights into the structure and complexity of the mixer operations. Indeed, by assessing the graph’s size and density, it is possible to infer the potential scale of the mixing process. Then, if multiple mixer addresses are identified within the same graph, the path between them is extracted and analysed using a visualisation tool (Gephi). This approach allows for an in-depth exploration of how these addresses are interconnected, revealing patterns of activity (or Relational Schemes - RSs) that might otherwise be obscured in raw data.

Phase 3: Inter-graph community analysis. In this phase, community detection techniques are used to detect dense topological structures within all

the mixer address-transaction graphs. Then clustering algorithms are used to group them according to topological similarity. Specifically, this phase envisages four steps. In the first one, for each graph, we apply the Louvain Community (LC) detection algorithm to extract the different communities (see Section 2.1). Once the communities are identified, in the second step of this phase, graph properties are extracted to describe each community topology. These metrics are selected by combining the outcomes of previous works [49–51], and are reported in Table 1. However, since 4 of these properties (degree, closeness, betweenness, and harmonic centrality) are node-level metrics, their values represent an average over all the nodes. Furthermore, for the degree property, the maximum and minimum values are also included. In the third step of this phase, these topological properties are used as input for clustering algorithms (HDBSCAN and OPTICS, see Section 2.2), to group communities that share similar properties. Finally, in the last step, the clusters are dissected, and those containing a higher number of known entities are further depicted using a visualisation tool (Gephi).

4 Experimental Study

In this section, an overview of the data, the sources and the model parameters used in this study is provided. In particular, Section 4.1 details the datasets and the source from which they are gathered, whereas Section 4.2 describes the parameters used for tuning the models as well as the metrics used to evaluate them.

4.1 Data Overview

As mentioned, the main objective of this work is to dissect the behaviour of the mixer *Blender.io*, highlighting economic attributes, dynamics, and relational patterns that can be used to define and remark its *MO*. To do that, the *Blender.io* addresses identified and sanctioned by the OFAC have been used as the starting point for this study. Specifically, at the paper date (Dec. 2024), the OFAC *Specially Designated Nationals and Blocked Persons* (SDN) list⁵ includes information about 45 *Blender.io* addresses only related to the Bitcoin network. Since the exact names of these addresses are not relevant and do not affect the aim of this work, an identifier (ID) from 1 to 45 has been assigned to each of them and used during the analysis.

To start with the study, all Bitcoin blockchain transactions until the paper date have been taken into account, i.e., more than 870k blocks and 1.120B transactions. At the same time, to link the *Blender.io* with other known real-world entities, labelled/tagged addresses are gathered from multiple sources, such as WalletExplorer⁶ and the GraphSense tagpacks [52]. These sources have been used as ‘ground-truth’ in many previous researches [53–55], and allowed us

⁵<https://sanctionssearch.ofac.treas.gov/>

⁶<https://www.walletexplorer.com/>

to gather more than 38M addresses of almost 400 entities labelled as *Exchanges*, *Gambling*, *Marketplaces*, *Mining Pools*, *Mixers*, *Services*, *Trading*, *eWallet* and *Ransomware*.

4.2 Metrics and Parameters

As introduced in Section 3, phase 3 involves various algorithms requiring parameter tuning. For the LC algorithm, the weights of the edges (e.g., the amounts sent or received) within the address-transaction graphs are considered during community generation and the resolution and threshold are set to default values, 1 and 1e-07, respectively. Additionally, for our analysis, all communities should be characterised by address nodes at the boundaries (i.e., only address nodes can have input degree or output degree = 0) and they must include at least one transaction node which must have both input degree and output degree $\neq 0$. This condition results in address nodes being shared between multiple communities, which is not supported by the LC algorithm (Section 2.1). Thus, we slightly modified the community detection process to include this specification.

Regarding the clustering algorithms, for both the HDBSCAN and OPTICS, the minimum number of samples for creating a cluster (*minPts*) is set to 5. Then, a study is conducted to evaluate how the ϵ parameter affects the OPTICS clusters and to determine the most suitable value for this use case. Specifically, 8 different values (0.1, 0.5, 0.9, 1, 1.5, 2, 3, 5) are tested. On the other hand, HDBSCAN does not require such a study, as it determines the optimal value internally (Section 2.2). Finally, to evaluate similarities between the OPTICS and HDBSCAN clusters, Adjusted Rand Index (ARI) [56] and Normalized Mutual Info (NMI) [57] scores were calculated. The first measures the proportion of correctly paired and unpaired elements (agreements), whereas the second measures the amount of information shared between two clusterings. Both metrics yield a score of 0 when they do not share information and 1 when two partitions are identical.

5 Results and Discussion

In this section, the obtained results are reported and discussed. In particular, Section 5.1 presents the results of Phase 1, while Sections 5.2 and 5.3 describe the results of Phases 2 and 3, respectively. Finally, limitations and discussion are provided in Section 5.4.

5.1 Economic Transaction Analysis

Before presenting the results of phase 1, an analysis of the temporality of the tx_{sout} and tx_{sin} is detailed. In particular, Figure 3 shows that all the mixer addresses are involved exactly in one tx_{sout} and one tx_{sin} , except for addresses with IDs 33 and 45. Figure 3 reveals that, in almost all the cases, the funds received by the mixer are immediately used as input for a new transaction.

A major delay can be observed in one specific case (ID 19), where the mixer address wait more time before moving the received funds. Additionally, Figure 3 highlights that mixer addresses are involved in activities in two concrete temporal instances: around blocks 650,000 (26/09/2020) and blocks 735,000 (05/05/2022). In this latter case, 19 addresses received and sent money almost simultaneously, just a month before being sanctioned.

Figure 3: Temporality of the tx_{sout} and tx_{sin} .

Figures 4a and 4b show that the input amounts of tx_{sout} are highly variable, ranging from ≤ 1 BTC (9 addresses) to the highest value of about 88 BTC (approx. \$8M at the time the transactions were performed) in 5 addresses. However, despite the high input variability, these figures indicate that the amount sent through tx_{sout} is not entirely sent to the mixer addresses. In fact, Figure 4a reports that in 22 cases, mixer addresses receive $\leq 35\%$ of the total amount sent as input in tx_{sout} , while the rest is sent to its siblings (other addresses involved in the tx_{sout} as outputs). This suggests a layered transaction model, where only part of the funds are directly processed by a single mixer address, while the rest is distributed across other entities to enhance anonymity. Figure 4b details that just in 9 cases the amount received exceeds 90%. Yet, the analysis also reveals that when the majority of the amount is sent to the mixer address, tx_{sout} typically have fees of around 1,000 satoshis (Figure 4b). On the other hand, when the majority of the amount is sent to mixer siblings, tx_{sout} shows fees of around 10,000 satoshis (Figure 4a).

Figures 4c and 4d analyse the characteristics of the transactions in which the mixer addresses spent the funds. Specifically, the figures show that in most

(a) tx_{sout} input analysis (part1).

(b) tx_{sout} input analysis (part2).

(c) tx_{sin} output analysis (part1)

(d) tx_{sin} output analysis (part2)

Figure 4: Input and output analysis of transactions tx_{sout} and tx_{sin} . Part 1 refers to mixer addresses that receive $\leq 35\%$ of the overall amount sent, while Part 2 includes addresses in the opposite scenario.

instances (25 addresses), the highest amount sent through a tx_{sin} is (almost) identically to the overall amount. This result suggests the presence of fund aggregation networks, where multiple amounts are combined into a single transaction with a unique output. This hypothesis is further confirmed by the fact that the majority of mixer addresses hold just small funds (Figures 4a and 4b) compared to the amounts sent through the tx_{sin} .

5.2 Intra-graph relational analysis

In this second phase, 23 address-transaction graphs have been created, which are able to link all the 45 labelled mixer addresses, as detailed in Table 2. Specifically, 15 of them do not show any connection between multiple mixer addresses. Among the others, one structure connects 12 mixer addresses within a single graph containing 355 addresses and 94 transactions (GI11), while another (GI19) connects just two mixer addresses within a complex network of 1,752 addresses and 120 transactions.

Graph Index	Mixer Starting Address	# Addresses	# TxS	Mixer Linked Address	Graph Index	Mixer Starting Address	# Addresses	# TxS	Mixer Linked Address
GI01	1	155	7	-	GI13	14	77	8	-
GI02	2	885	35	32	GI14	16	167	8	43
GI03	3	63	10	-	GI15	19	71	5	-
GI04	4	82	5	-	GI16	20	86	5	-
GI05	5	111	6	-	GI17	21	102	5	-
GI06	6	236	8	22, 36	GI18	23	53	9	-
GI07	7	419	6	-	GI19	24	1,752	120	42
GI08	8	373	46	11, 18, 27	GI20	35	222	9	-
GI09	9	176	12	25, 44	GI21	37	136	34	-
GI10	10	130	36	28	GI22	40	108	7	-
GI11	12	355	94	15, 17, 26, 29, 30, 31, 33, 34, 38, 39, 41	GI23	45	396	45	-
GI12	13	21	6	-					

Table 2: Information extracted from address-transaction graph in two steps.

Analysing the 9 address-transaction graphs that relate multiple mixer addresses within, and visually evaluating their paths, all of them can be generalised using the 4 Relational Schemes reported in Table 3. Following their definitions, it is evident that RS1 and RS2, represent forms for aggregating the funds (directly or in one step, respectively), while RS3 and RS4 represent how to split the funds (with multiple siblings or in a peeling chain). However, RS1 and RS4 are anticipated structures, as they reflect the expected behaviours of these entities. Yet, these two topologies are the most common structures, used across many address-transaction graphs. Specifically, RS4 appears 13 times across 5 different graphs, while RS1 appears 4 times across 4 graphs. In contrast, RS2 and RS3 are less common, appearing in just 2 and 1 graphs, respectively.

5.3 Inter-graph community analysis

The first step of phase 3 (Section 3) extracts 208 communities from the 23 address-transaction graphs using the LC-modified algorithm (Section 4). Figure 5a shows that most of them (116) are characterised by less than 10 nodes (both address and transaction), while few structures link more than 200 nodes.

Relational Scheme	Description	Graph Index (Address IDs)
	<p>RS1: Multiple mixer addresses are used as inputs in the same tx_{sin}, recalling an aggregation network;</p>	<p>GI06(6,22,36); GI09(9, 25,44); GI11(12,26, 29,30,33,34, 38,39,41); GI14(16,43);</p>
	<p>RS2: Multiple mixer addresses send money to their respective tx_{sin}, whose outputs participate in an aggregation network;</p>	<p>GI08(8,27); GI11(15,31);</p>
	<p>RS3: A mixer address (a_y) has a sibling in tx_{sout} that, in turn, participates in an aggregation network, with a mixer address (a_{y+1}) as the output</p>	<p>GI19(24,42);</p>
	<p>RS4: A mixer address (a_y) has a sibling in tx_{sout} that, in turn, sends money to exactly 2 addresses, one of which is a mixer address, resembling a first step of a peeling chain;</p>	<p>GI02(42,2); GI08(11,18); GI08(18,8); GI08(8,27); GI09(25,44); GI10(10,28); GI11(33,30); GI11(30,26); GI11(26,29); GI11(38,34); GI11(34,39); GI11(31,12); GI11(15,17);</p>

Table 3: Relational Schemes (RSs) identified using the visualisation tool, with information about the graphs index (GI) and address IDs that resemble each one. Edges are coloured according to the sender node.

In the second and third steps, topological properties are extracted and used as input for clustering algorithms. Figure 5b analyses the performance of the OPTICS algorithm when different ϵ values are used. Specifically, the figure shows that increasing the ϵ results in more elements being clustered, reducing the number of outliers (no clustered elements). Consequently, the number of distinct clusters increases. However, this trend is verified only up to a specific threshold ($\epsilon=1.5$), after that, no further changes occur in the cluster numbers and composition. This threshold represents the point at which the number of clustered communities reaches its maximum, and for this, it is chosen as the reference value for comparing OPTICS with the HDBSCAN clusters. As shown in Figure 5c, OPTICS ($\epsilon=1.5$) and HDBSCAN produced similar results, forming highly aligned groups. This aspect is highlighted also by ARI and NMI scores of 0.70 and 0.86, respectively. The main (small) differences lie in three aspects: i) OPTICS generates 13 clusters plus outliers, while HDBSCAN creates 12 clusters plus outliers; ii) OPTICS identifies over 60 outliers (cluster ID -1), compared to 51 in HDBSCAN, with 45 overlapping; iii) HDBSCAN's cluster ID 4 includes 10 more elements than OPTICS. This general alignment in the HDBSCAN and OPTICS results confirms the robustness of the obtained clusters, suggesting that the identified patterns are consistent across different clustering techniques. This similarity also suggests that the clusters are not overly sensitive to the specific algorithm used.

(a) Communities histogram according to their number of nodes. (b) OPTICS clustering results with different ϵ values.

(c) OPTICS vs HDBSCAN clusters. Outliers in cluster ID -1. (d) Known entities in each cluster.

Figure 5: Results of the different steps of phase 3.

In the fourth step, the composition of clusters in terms of known entities is analysed, considering only the shared structures between OPTICS and HDBSCAN. Figure 5d highlights that *Exchange* entities are the most prevalent, whereas other entities (*Mixer* and *Service*) appear only in a few instances. This represents an interesting result, as the majority of *Exchange* must comply with AML/KYC regulations and should control the origin of the funds, ensuring they do not deal with sanctioned entities.

Looking at Figure 5d, cluster ID 4 contains more than 50 *Exchange* addresses distributed across over 15 communities, out of the 17 communities shared by the HDBSCAN and OPTICS. Similarly, clusters with IDs 7 and 8 also include a significant number of *Exchange* addresses spread across many communities. This underscores the predominant role of *Exchange* entities in mixer activities. Figure 6A represents the predominant topology in cluster ID 4, followed by 11 out of 17 communities within this cluster. These communities are characterised by two transaction nodes (TX_1 and TX_2) connected by exactly two addresses: one address receives funds from both TX_1 and TX_2 , while the other receives a significant amount from TX_1 and forwards it to TX_2 without splitting it. Notably, these communities do not share the same numbers of inputs for TX_1 and output for TX_2 . Additionally, when this predominant topology is enriched with labelled information, it reveals that *Exchange* addresses are primarily the input of TX_1 and the output of TX_2 with the highest amount. Figure 6B draws the predominant topology of communities in cluster ID 7 (15 out of 19), while Figure 6C show the topology followed in cluster ID 8 (12 out of 13). The topologies in these clusters are very similar: featuring a single transaction node that receives a significant amount from one address and then distributes the funds to 4 or 5 addresses, according to the cluster. Furthermore, when these topologies are enriched with labelled information, they show that the input and the output with the highest received amount are both *Exchange* addresses.

Figure 6: Predominant community topologies within cluster IDs 4, 7, and 8. The width of the edges indicates the amount sent/received.

5.4 Discussion

Dissecting the results, several key aspects can be extracted with the aim of identifying the mixer’s *MO*. As a first dimension, results reveal that mixer addresses immediately use the received funds as input in new transactions. This behaviour may suggest a deliberate strategy to minimise detection and increase

the complexity of traceability, and it becomes particularly relevant if the mixer’s owners are aware of impending sanctions, allowing them to move funds to a safer location in advance. Additionally, the analysis shows that most of the mixer addresses are involved in aggregating funds into a single address. Then, as a second dimension, the study reveals that mixer addresses received only a portion of the total amount sent in the transactions. The analysis uncovers a common structure in which multiple mixer addresses are interconnected, forming primarily four distinct Relational Schemes, with two of them (RS1: aggregation network and R4: peeling chain) emerging as the most frequent and critical pattern in the mixer’s operations. Finally, as a third dimension of the mixer’s *MO*, the inter-graph community analysis reveals consistent structural patterns across address-transaction graphs, allowing clustering algorithms to group similar communities. The analysis shows that *Exchanges* play a key role in mixer operations since they appear in many communities following a well-established pattern, and raising several concerns about their AML/KYC policy.

Limitation. When interpreting the results, it is important to consider the constraints applied during this investigation. Firstly, the entire study is based on analysing the activities of *Blender.io* in the Bitcoin network provided by the US OFAC authority, while other agencies (OFSI, EEAS, etc.) either lack such information or do not release it publicly. Therefore, the obtained results should be validated when new information about the mixer (within the Bitcoin network and in other blockchains) becomes available. On the other hand, phase 3 results strongly depend on the quantity and quality of labelled data available in the literature. The 38M labelled addresses used in this study represent less than 3% of the existing Bitcoin addresses, however, they remain the best open-source dataset available for research purposes. Regarding the quality of this information, we rely on the fact that it has been used in numerous research investigations [53, 54] and, in some cases, extracted by sources and tools used in real investigations. Moreover, although these datasets are generated and gathered from different sources, they do not exhibit inconsistencies.

6 Conclusion and Future Work

This work introduces a systematic graph-based approach to analyse economic and topological patterns for uncovering mixers’ *Modus Operandi (MO)*. The methodology uses reduced address-transaction graphs across three phases: economic transaction analysis, intra-graph relational analysis, and inter-graph community analysis. Validating the approach with *Blender.io* activities within the Bitcoin blockchain, it identifies three dimensions of the mixer’s *MO*: 1) mixer’s addresses primarily aggregate funds into a single address; 2) multiple mixer addresses are linked within the same activity graph, (mainly) resembling a peeling chain; 3) mixer activities create communities that follow similar, well-structured topological patterns. Additionally, the visualisation tool highlights the key role of *Exchanges* in mixer operations. This work represents a preliminary step, offering an intriguing yet partial view of how mixers’ operational structures

can be analysed. Despite its limitations, these findings provide insights to help LEAs focus efforts on specific aspects of criminal operations, gather evidence for prosecutions, and extract *MO* dimensions across multiple cases.

In future work, a deeper exploration of the economic aspects of address-transaction graphs and the integration of temporal information will be valuable. The first factor will help develop an intelligent module to highlight high-risk transactions and addresses, helping officers identify aggregation networks and money laundering schemes. The temporality will introduce a dynamic aspect, revealing trends in fund movements over time and uncovering patterns like peak activity periods linked to criminal operations. Furthermore, visual analytics approaches can be incorporated to evaluate the findings using specific metrics, going beyond simple visualisations. By incorporating these elements, we aim to improve investigative approaches providing more actionable intelligence, and strengthening their overall capacity for detecting criminal *Modus Operandi*.

Author contributions

Francesco Zola: Conceptualisation, Methodology, Investigation, Writing- Original draft preparation. Jon Ander Medina: Conceptualisation, Data curation, Resources. Andrea Venturi: Resources, Writing - Review & Editing. Raul Orduna: Supervision and Writing - Review & Editing.

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